

ORTHOGONAL STITCHING OF 2D FABRICS FOR IMPROVED DELAMINATION RESISTANCE

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1. Introduction

1.1 Laminated Composites

Fibre/fabric reinforced textile composite materials usually comprise 2D textile structures. As a consequence of their comparatively weak through-the-thickness mechanical properties, they suffer substantially from delamination when exposed to out-of-plane loading. To improve the delamination resistance of multilayered textile composites, 3D braiding, 3D weaving and stitching have been widely used as a means of conferring through-the-thickness reinforcement. Of these approaches to z-direction reinforcement, it has been found that the insertion of stitching is an effective way to counter crack propagation and to prevent delamination inside multi-layer composites [1-3].

1.2 Stitching of Preforms

Consequently, those classes of seam that are commonly used in the assembly of clothing have been applied to multi-layer composites in various attempts to improve the delamination performance of these structures. The most straightforward of the machine-made seams are designated as class 100; the single-thread chain-stitches. The ISO# 101 is a chainstitch which can be created using a single thread, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 ISO# 101 Chainstitch [4].

This seam offers the advantage that it can be created using a single thread which is intra-looped by using the sewing needle to pass each successive stitch through the loop of the previous stitch. Its simplicity facilitates its formation by a relatively uncomplicated mechanism which is capable of operating at high speed. The simple construction process ensures that the sewing thread is subjected to only minor mechanical manipulation during the insertion of the seam. Commercial chainstitch sewing machines operate satisfactorily over a wide range of thread tensions. By setting a particularly low needle thread tension, even delicate laminates demonstrate little tendency to buckle as a result of the tensile forces introduced by the needle thread, and similarly, the reinforcing thread also avoids being subjected to significant tensile loading. Nevertheless, chainstitching has been reported to cause significant fabric damage in high-performance reinforcement fabrics [5, 6].

The geometrical properties of the chainstitch are less advantageous for the creation of laminated composite structures. Although two z-direction threads are introduced into the laminate at each needle insertion point, the seam features a discontinuous line of thread on the upper surface of the laminate and two repeatedly looped threads on the lower surface. Hence three lengths of surface thread, which contribute little to the structural properties of the resulting composite, accompany each pair of vertical threads. Furthermore, each loop on the underside of the finished structure incorporates a small radius 360° bend which is severely deleterious to the tensile properties of the high-performance yarns which are likely to be used in such situations [7].

The inefficient thread utilisation, which is unavoidable with the chainstitch, may be addressed

by the use of class 300 lockstitches for laminate consolidation. The ISO# 301 lockstitch offers a neat appearance on both sides and allows different threads to be used for the upper and lower components of the seam. This stitch also offers highly efficient thread utilisation, as may be seen in Figure 2, and is the only type of commercial seam which can be successfully turned through a right-angled corner.

Fig. 2 ISO# 301 Lockstitch [8].

Of the two threads that are used to generate the lockstitch seam, the upper one is supplied via the sewing needle and the lower thread is provided by a bobbin mounted in a demountable case which is located beneath the bed of the machine. Each stitch of the lockstitch seam is formed by interlacing the needle-thread and the bobbin-thread. In practice, this involves expanding a loop of thread from the sewing needle so that it may pass completely over the bobbin case. Once it has passed over the bobbin case, the excess thread is then pulled back through the eye of the needle so that it just encircles the bobbin thread. The needle thread is finally tensioned so that the interlacement point of the stitch is pulled up into the fabric substrate to create a balanced lockstitch. The balanced ISO# 301 lockstitch seam is completely symmetrical; only a single line of stitching is located on the upper and lower surfaces of the composite laminate, and two threads are inserted in the z-direction to consolidate the structure at each penetration point.

Unfortunately, the formation of the seam is not a straightforward process and the mechanism required to interlace the two threads is relatively complex. The expansion of the needle thread around the bobbin case during stitch formation is achieved by a rotary hook which circles around the bobbin case. Two revolutions of this under-bed mechanism are required to form a single stitch, hence the rotary hook is required to spin at twice the speed of the needle reciprocation and this limits the speed of the lockstitch sewing operation to approximately half

that of the chainstitch machine. The needle thread is also subjected to severe loading as a small loop is gathered and subjected to significantly elevated tension during its passage around the bobbin case [9]. The necessity to pass the needle thread around the bobbin case places restrictions on the capacity of the bobbin and this in turn limits the length of seam that may be inserted before renewing the bobbin of thread. The formation of a balanced lockstitch seam also necessitates a relatively high needle thread tension which can induce puckering in delicate structures. This problem is compounded by the fact that comparatively long lengths of thread are repeatedly passed through the eye of the needle during stitch formation. The frictional interaction between thread and eye imposes a significant heating effect on the needle which has to be controlled by limiting the speed of operation or by forced-air needle cooling, otherwise the thread lubricant will be degraded and the frictional problems will be deteriorate further.

From a geometrical point of view, the performance of the conventional lockstitch is limited by the fact that the through-thickness reinforcement is provided by two interlaced loops, each of which features a small-radius 360° loop. So the problem discussed earlier in respect of the chainstitch geometry is present in an even more severe incarnation in the conventional lockstitch seam. The two loops together form the reinforcement yarns, and thus present a limiting factor for the applicability of this stitch.

1.3 Practical Composite Consolidation

As a consequence of the geometrical shortcomings of the balanced lockstitch seam, the lockstitch seams employed to consolidate composite products are almost invariably inserted into composite structures using a modified form, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 The Modified Lockstitch [8].

The modified lockstitch seam is created using the same commercial sewing machinery as is used for

standard lockstitch creation. Seam production is modified by reducing the tension of the bobbin thread, by adjustment of the leaf spring tensioning element fitted to the bobbin case and increasing the needle thread tension. Thus, instead of drawing the interlacement point up into the middle of the laminate by balancing the counter-tension of the bobbin thread, the needle thread has sufficient excess tension to pull it through to the upper surface of the structure. The upper thread ends up flat on the upper surface of the composite structure, as seen in Figure 3, and the bobbin thread forms both strands of the z-direction reinforcement. There are a number of advantages embodied in the modified form of the lockstitch; the vertical threads follow a straight path and which is not disrupted by an interlacement point and the number of 360° small-radius loops is halved. Unfortunately, the interlacement loop formation cannot be dispensed with completely and the lockstitch creation process unavoidably exerts undesirable tensile stresses on the upper thread during the manufacture of the seam. In the final modified lockstitch, however, the upper thread would appear to play a relatively minor role.

An alternative form of stitched reinforcement has also been considered for the role of providing through-thickness delamination resistance to multi-layer composites. This is the ISO# 205 topstitch, otherwise termed the orthogonal stitch, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. The Orthogonal Stitch.
The fabric plies are horizontal and the stitching is in contrasting colour.

Although traditionally classed as a hand stitch, this type of seam can be generated using a sewing machine, although all the experimental work in this research has been performed manually. This inevitably means that the results are likely to suffer from tension variation and may be improved upon when they are created by machine. As can be seen from the simple form of the stitch, the seam is devoid of intra-looping or interlacement, both of which techniques unavoidably introduce small radius curves which degrade the performance of

textile threads. The bends in the orthogonal seam are all nominally 90° and with some applied tension on the thread and compression of the substrate these angles are likely, in practice, to become slightly larger radius curves. It would appear, therefore, that the geometrical form of the orthogonal stitch may offer advantages over the modified lockstitch which is currently the default seam used for providing through-the-thickness reinforcement for laminated fibre preforms in the manufacture of composite structures. It also offers efficient thread utilisation, with only a single sequence of discontinuous stitches thread appearing on the surface of the composite for each sequence of single thread through-thickness insertions; these are divided between the upper and lower surfaces.

In order to equate the through-thickness reinforcement with that of the modified lockstitch which has two z-direction reinforcement threads at each needle penetration point, a doubled thread was also used to provide a strengthened form of the orthogonal stitch. This could be inserted without increasing the number of penetrations of the composite structure, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 The Doubled Orthogonal Stitch.
The fabric plies are horizontal and the stitching is in contrasting colours.

If generated with the same pitch as the modified lockstitch, the doubled orthogonal stitch offers the same number of z-direction reinforcement threads. Both the modified lockstitch and the doubled orthogonal stitch lay the equivalent of a single line of thread on the upper and lower surfaces of the composite preform. Thread utilisation will be very similar for the two stitch geometries, the major difference between the seams in respect of delamination will be the absence of small radius loops in the doubled orthogonal stitching.

This research was designed to examine the coherence of multi-component 3D textile composites by using different geometries of through-the-thickness stitched reinforcement as well as unstitched multi-layer structures. Several different

types of stitching have been used to provide z-direction strengthening in recent years as identified by Morales [8] and later revisited by Dransfield, Baillie and Mai [2]; all feature 360° loops which provide a structural weakness. To address this geometrical problem, orthogonal stitching has been used to consolidate the fabric layers in the preform. An orthogonal stitch and a doubled orthogonal stitch have been evaluated alongside the standard z-direction reinforcement technique of modified lockstitch. The delamination resistance of test samples made with these three forms of stitching has been used to examine the extent to which the 360° small-radius loops inherent in the modified lockstitch geometry coupled with the demanding lockstitch production process cause significant loss of performance in the class 300 seams.

2. Experimental Method

2.1 Z-direction Preform Stitching

In this experimental work, eight layers of glass fibre fabric were used to make a large preform panel. From this panel, a number of different test specimens were created in semi-random sequence, some stitched and some left in the unstitched state. By creating all the test specimens from the same fabric lay-up it was intended that the various test pieces would consequently be subjected to identical manufacturing conditions. Some of the test specimens were stitched using an Adler KL 267 upholstery machine which, although designed for automotive seat stitching, nonetheless formed a standard ISO# 301 lockstitch. This machine was threaded with nylon 6.6 yarn (in the sewing needle) and a multi-filament glass yarn (on the bobbin) and these threads were used to generate a modified lockstitch. It was found to be necessary to significantly increase the needle yarn tension and reduce the bobbin tension in order to satisfactorily produce the unbalanced lockstitch seams, hence the use of nylon yarn as the needle thread; it is more robust in respect of surviving the rigours of the manufacturing process. Other sections of the preform panel were sewn with alternative stitch formations. These were created by hand, using either a single multi-filament glass yarn or a doubled multi-filament glass yarn, so that the ISO# 205 orthogonal seams might be inserted into the test

panels. The glass yarn was the same as that used in the creation of the modified lockstitch stitches. All the seams provided through-the-thickness bridging and those samples that were deliberately left unstitched were used to provide comparative evidence of the effectiveness of stitching composite structures.

2.2 Manufacture of Composite Samples

To make up the test samples, eight sheets of 2x2 twill woven E-glass were used to ensure that the test pieces would each be between 3mm and 5mm thick, so that they would conform to the specifications of the ASTM D5528-01 test procedure [10]. The rectangles of fabric were laid up with the warp directions of each layer aligned. The lay-up was 320mm long, in the warp direction and 390mm wide, in the weft direction, and was therefore large enough for a multiplicity of test samples to be made from this single fabrication. The upper surface was then inscribed with the specific dimensions as required by the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) standard test procedure; test pieces of 25mm width and 125mm length were marked. As part of this process, 62mm of the length was designated as a stitching area, and the remaining 63mm of fabric was left unstitched. The unstitched section forms the initial delamination length into which release film is inserted to facilitate the test procedure.

Fig. 6 The lay-up of the test fabrics showing the insertion of orthogonal stitching into one area.

The outlined penetration areas of the test lay-up were then stitched within the marked areas, as shown in Figure 6. Each sample was sewn with the same density of stitches using one of the three different stitch geometries that were under test. A selection of differing stitch lengths were applied and a number of different spacings were adopted between the rows of stitches inserted into the test panels. To ensure that the orthogonal hand stitches were inserted with at the same density as the modified lockstitching, the insertion points were marked on the surface of the DCB samples. Most of the DCB test samples were thus provided with z-direction consolidation using either modified lockstitch, orthogonal or doubled orthogonal stitch types. The remaining samples were left unstitched for comparative purposes.

Prior to resin infusion, non-adhesive Aerovac-A6000 ETFE release film, with a thickness of 20 μ m, was used to separate the upper and lower halves of the non-stitched areas of the preform by inserting it between the upper four layers and the lower four layers of the 63mm unstitched section of the test pieces in the preform. This process was performed prior to the initiation of the vacuuming process in order to ensure that the upper and lower sections of the unstitched areas of the test panels would still be divided along their mid-plane following resin infusion. The whole preform, comprising the semi-randomly distributed combination of the four different types of test specimen was then placed in commercial vacuum forming equipment, and was infused with a two part degassed epoxy encapsulation medium in the ratio of 100 parts of Bisphenol A resin (Araldite LV 564) to 34 parts of hardener (Aradur XB 3486). After injection, the infused composite panel was cured in an autoclave at 80°C for 8 hours.

Finally, the individual rectangular test specimens, sized at 25mm x 125mm, were separated using a water-cooled diamond saw. To prepare the DCB composite test specimens for Mode I Interlaminar fracture toughness testing, metal loading hinges of 25mm width and 13mm length were mounted on the upper and lower surfaces at the unstitched end of the 63mm test specimens. These hinges are visible in Figure 7 which shows a specimen under test.

2.3 Test Method

To investigate the delamination resistance of the multi-layered stitched and unstitched E-Glass/Epoxy composite specimens, Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was measured using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) testing method as specified under the ASTM D5528–01 standard method [10]. The tests were performed using an Instron model 8862 tensile testing machine. The procedure was for each of the pre-delaminated DCB composite test specimens to be clamped by inserting one of the loading hinges into each of a pair of flat-faced jaws in the Instron machine, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7 A hinged composite test specimen subjected to delamination testing.

The test was initially set up with the jaws of the tensile tester positioned at a suitable displacement so that the test specimen could be mounted free from load. Then tensile extension was carried out using a pre-set constant crosshead speed of 5mm/min.

The test specimens were initially drawn at the pre-set speed for one minute, so that 5mm of displacement was applied. Then the side of the specimen was inspected with an optical microscope to see whether unsteady crack growth from the insert might be detected. If this was the case, then the specimens were dismantled from the tensile tester and the ends of the cracks were pinpointed to check

the difference in crack length on either side of the specimen.

The DCB composite test specimens were then reloaded and the testing resumed at the same extension speed as applied initially. This was maintained for the remainder of the test, during which time the specimens were tested to failure, and the crack growth of the specimens was systematically captured using an optical microscope.

3. Results and Discussion

For the unstitched composite specimens, it was observed that inter-laminar cracks grew relatively easily and specimens invariably delaminated along their full length, as illustrated in Figure 8, and they consistently demonstrated the lowest level of fracture toughness.

Fig. 8 Delamination along the full length of an unstitched specimen.

Monitoring of the stitched composite specimens during the testing process showed that crack propagation proceeded more gradually and whilst some specimens demonstrated crack propagation and ultimately delaminated along the full length of the mid-layer, as did the unstitched samples, many of the stitched specimens suffered other modes of failure, whether reinforced with modified lockstitch seams, orthogonal stitching or doubled orthogonal stitches. A stitched specimen that is undergoing Mode I interlaminar fracture testing and is in the process of full delamination may be clearly seen in Figure 7.

A photomicrograph of the cross-section of a typical failed sample reinforced with stitches of modified lockstitch geometry is shown in Figure 9. The

fractured ends of the multi-filament E-glass reinforcement thread can clearly be seen and the stitching appears to have failed indiscriminately both along the fracture line and to either side of the delamination path.

Fig. 9 Cross-section of a failed sample reinforced with modified lockstitching.

A cross-section of a failed specimen reinforced with single orthogonal stitching is shown in Figure 10. In this instance, the multi-filament E-glass reinforcement has consistently failed along the crack propagation delamination path.

Fig. 10 Cross-section of a failed sample reinforced with orthogonal stitching.

An overall detailed comparison of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness results for all the different specimen structures has been collated and

is illustrated in the bar chart shown in Fig. 11. The top bar on the graph presents the averaged results obtained for the fracture toughness of the unstitched composite specimens and these can be seen to be, by some margin, the weakest specimens that have been tested, with results around 1.1kJm^{-2} .

Fig. 11 Delamination resistance of different reinforcement stitch types

The other results are clustered into five groups of three different stitch types, and within each group the stitch density is the same, which allows straightforward comparison of the effectiveness of the three different types of stitched consolidation. Each of the samples in the lower three clusters of results was consolidated with a single column of stitching. In the lowest group, the stitches were 20mm in length, as marked on the graph, in the next group the stitches were 10mm in length and in the most densely stitched of the single column samples, the stitch length was 5mm.

For these three groups of single-column results it can be seen that the toughness of the modified lockstitch samples gradually increases with stitch density. The samples consolidated with single orthogonal stitching are consistently the poorest performers and return similar results for 20mm and 10mm stitching but produce higher results for the 5mm stitching. The samples for which doubled orthogonal stitching has been used exceed the performance of the modified lockstitch samples at the longest stitch length, and actually decrease in fracture toughness for the 10mm stitch length group

and return results just below those of the modified lockstitching in the 5mm stitch length group.

It should be noted that insertion of the sewing needle causes damage to the fabrics that compose the substrate and the amount of damage inevitably increases with repeated needle penetration as the stitch density is increased.

The two upper clusters of results in the graph of Figure 11 are for samples which were reinforced with twin columns of stitching. The top group (marked 5x5) was sewn with two rows of 5mm stitches separated by 5mm, this was therefore the highest stitch density of any of the tests. The group below (marked 10x10) was sewn with two rows of 10mm stitches positioned 10mm apart.

The delamination resistance of the twin column samples is higher than that produced for the single-column tests. The single yarn orthogonal stitching produced results of 2.5kJm^{-2} for the 10x10 samples and 3.5kJm^{-2} for the 5x5 samples. The modified lockstitch results were particularly high for the 10x10 samples at over 3.5kJm^{-2} , but fell below 3.5kJm^{-2} for the highest density (5x5) stitching. The double thread orthogonal reinforcement barely exceeded 2.5kJm^{-2} for the 10x10 samples, but produced the highest results of all the trials for the 5x5 samples, at almost 3.9kJm^{-2} .

4. Conclusions

The overall test results seen in Figure 11 compare multi-layer composite specimens made using preforms in which the strata were either unstitched or were reinforced in the z-direction with a number of different stitch types. The reinforcement was achieved by inserting either modified lockstitching using nylon and glass yarns, orthogonal stitching with a single glass yarn or orthogonal stitching with a doubled glass yarn.

It was found in every case that stitching through-the-thickness reinforcement into composite laminates increases Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness against interlaminar delamination. Inevitably, the more dense the stitching that is inserted, the greater will be the needle damage to the textile fabrics which provide structural reinforcement to the composite in the x and y directions.

Amongst the stitching techniques employed for through-the-thickness reinforcement which were used in this experimental study it can be seen that

applying modified orthogonal stitching improves interlaminar strength and high delamination resistance can be gained. Modified lockstitch is the most commonly used type of z-direction reinforcement and serves as a useful standard against which the orthogonal stitching technique can be judged.

In none of the considered cases does single orthogonal stitching prove to provide more effective z-direction consolidation than either the modified lockstitch or the double orthogonal stitch; it does, nonetheless, show itself to be very effective performer, producing figures which are comparable with stitches which feature double the number of z-direction threads. In circumstances in which test samples feature both the highest and the lowest stitch densities, the double orthogonal stitching provides the most effective through-the thickness reinforcement. In all the intermediate cases, it is the modified lockstitch reinforcement that provides the best consolidation to protect against interlaminar delamination.

It should be borne in mind that all the orthogonal stitching has been created manually and that more accurate tension control and vertical needle alignment may make the stitch more consistent and further improve its performance. Conversely, it is possible that the care with which the orthogonal stitching has been inserted may have created less damage to the fabrics in the lay-up and stitching with a lower thread tension may have already provided some advantage to the orthogonal and double orthogonal stitch sequences.

It can, furthermore, be concluded that the value of interlaminar fracture toughness of the orthogonal stitched composite specimen groups increases as the number of stitched reinforcement columns in the sample is increased. The delamination resistance of orthogonal stitching clearly improves as the stitch density of the reinforcement is increased, as a consequence of reduced stitch length and decreased separation between adjacent seams. The strength of the reinforcement has been shown to depend upon the density of the z-direction fibre insertions and in the circumstances that have been examined the orthogonal stitch types have been shown to provide a more predictable performance than does modified lockstitching.

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